

Voice Gender Recognition

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Abstract:- Due to its widespread application in a variety of circumstances, the gender classification system has become more and more relevant including social media platforms and criminal investigations. Prior studies in this area have mostly focused on discrimination against both men and women. Nevertheless, since transgender persons have just received legal recognition, it has been vital to create techniques for accurately diagnosing gender from a specific voice, which can be a challenging undertaking. To extract pertinent characteristics from a training set that may be utilised to create a model for gender categorization, researchers have employed a number of techniques. Following then, a vocal signal's gender may be ascertained using this model. The study makes three significant contributions: first, it provides a thorough analysis of well-known voice signal features using a well-known dataset; second, it investigates a variety of machine learning models from a variety of theoretical families to classify voice gender; and third, it uses three well-known feature selection algorithms to select the features that have the greatest potential to improve classification models.

Keywords:- Python, Machine Learning, Transformer, TensorFlow, Spectrogram, Matplotlib, Pandas, HTML, CSS, Django.

I. INTRODUCTION

Gender can be determined by using speech and voice recognition technology. Based on the frequency and volume of a person's voice and speech, the ear has an excellent system for determining their gender. A method known as machine learning voice recognition employs machine learning algorithms to assist computers in comprehending and interpreting spoken language. The algorithm is fed a lot of labelled data during the training process, allowing it to learn from examples and get better over time. When the AI calculation has been prepared, it tends to be utilized to perceive and decipher human discourse continuously. Virtual assistants, speech-to-text transcription, language translation, and voice-controlled devices like smart speakers and home automation systems are just a few of the many uses for this technology.

II. LITRATURE REVIEW

After studying the existing publications that are relevant to the idea of our proposed system, we found out that a huge amount of voice gender recognition models are built on Support Vector Machine (SVM), CART, Random Forest, and deep learning techniques like Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) and GBM [1][2][3][7][8][9]. Several programs have helped with gender classification in the past, but only for men and females, not transgender people. One of the findings was that it uses gender and language to identify the language of spoken utterances and identify the speaker's gender based on their voice. Some of them use orthographic transcription accomplished by recording and analyzing the speaker's speech using the Gaussian Mixture Model and MFCC feature extraction called automatic speech recognition (ASR) and semi-supervised learning [4][5][13] focus male and female only. The transformer input layer is used to implement ASR and Transformer Keras voice recognition, Librosa, Mel Spectrogram which interprets audio waves to identify transgenders from male and female voice datasets. In order to create classifiers that are more accurate, current research focuses on fusing ensemble learning strategies with semi-supervised learning frameworks. Making emotional speech understandable in order to determine the speaker's gender makes the challenge even more intriguing [6][10]. Recently, a number of cutting-edge gender recognition methods based on several biometrics, including the face, body form, and voice, have been presented. The worst one of them is relying solely on voice. Voice verification, gender categorization from voice, and native (mother tongue) linguistic context were all explored. Four classifiers are used in a stacked ensemble for gender voice identification as the basis classifiers: LR, KNN, SVM, SGD, and LDA [11][12][14].

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The VOICE GENDER RECOGNITION proposes to solve the classification of genders through voice not only in males and females but also to include transgenders. System design of multiple technologies are included in voice gender recognition. The system uses Python and machine learning for the backend and HTML, CSS, Django, and JavaScript for the front-end development. Here, algorithms will help in the

classification of the genders by matching the extracted data from the provided input with the stored dataset. In order to host the programme on the website, a user interface is also created. The Voice Gender Recognition GUI is designed in the first place, on a website. Users can offer speech data to be recognised as input on the website thanks to a voice fetch mechanism. The model is created using machine learning methods in the way that follows:

- Extraction of data Machine learning is a process in which the data is extracted from an original source, and then it is processed to obtain information. In order to extract the data from the .wav audio file, we use Spectrogram.
- Training the data Fitting a model to fresh data is the process of machine learning. The main aim of the training is to identify the model's ideal parameters. To discover these parameters in practice, we often employ an optimisation approach (such as gradient descent). Machine learning training is the process of developing a model from unstructured data. We use Python, Spectrogram, Transformer, TensorFlow, matplotlib, PyCharm, NumPy, Pandas and Jupyter Notebook.
- All the acoustic features are extracted with the use of librosa library, it is then stored in .csv file for further processing. Pattern matching is the collection of tasks performed by various Machine Learning tools like pandas, matplotlib etc., for identifying trends.

A. Supervised Learning and Classification of Rules

One can classify rules based on the information they contain with supervised learning. It can be very useful for finding patterns in our data that will help us decide which rule to apply to a new situation or case more effectively.

B. Voice Gender Recognition

The ML-based voice identification tool takes the .wav audio file as input from the user, and will first extract the features using R Programming, it is then stored in .csv file for further processing. Pattern matching is performed to identify the trends by using various ML tools like matplotlib, and pandas etc., Based on the pattern matchings and various trends the decision logic algorithms like SVM, XGBoost etc., come into play for identifying gender and put the final decision.

Fig 1 System Flow Diagram

C. CSV Dataset

Wav file is a sound format that can be played in Windows Media Player, QuickTime and even iTunes. The .wav extension stands for Waveform Audio File and it was created by Microsoft.

➤ Implementation

This project's primary goal is to address the issue of trans-gender voice gender recognition. The implementation makes use of the following programmes, devices, or frameworks:

D. Web Design

Any system includes a large portion called the Graphical User Interface (GUI). An Audio file entry Page has been made with the aid of HTML, CSS, Django, and JavaScript utilising the UI of VOICE GENDER RECOGNITION. The website is utilised to get user voice data in .wav file format. The audio file is further processed as input speech to the machine learning model, which in the backend performs pattern-matching algorithms to give the most accurate result possible which is then displayed to the user.

Fig 2 GUI Implementation

E. Workflow Graph

Figure 4, explains how the whole workflow is done in the whole project. The graph completes each step of the project very accurately. The training phase describes how the model

Fig 3 Web UI for input

Is being trained for male, female, and transgender voices and which is then tested with an untouched dataset in the testing phase.

Fig 4 Web UI for Input

F. Workflow & Process Definition for Final Model

The process of analyzing a speech signal to extract relevant information in a form that is smaller than the speech signal itself is known as speech analysis. Multiple application domains make extensive use of AI and machine learning. Vectors of features An ordered list of numerical properties of observed phenomena is called a feature vector. A prediction-making machine learning model uses it as input features. Decisions can be made by humans by analyzing qualitative data. A conceptual framework that standardizes communication between diverse networks is provided by reference models.

G. Transformer Keras Voice recognition

A transformer is a machine-learning technique that utilizes self-attention mechanisms for sequential input data processing. It has become more widely used as a method for completing numerous natural language processing (NLP) tasks, including

Fig 5 Workflow & Process Definition for Final Model

Text summarization, sentiment analysis, and language translation. The self-attention feature enables the model to weigh different parts of the input in the representation of the input sequence. To do this, attention weights are calculated for each point in the input sequence depending on how similar the current position is to all other positions in the series. There are two types of transformers: an encoder and a decoder. The former processes the input sequence, generating hidden representations for each input position. The latter generates the output sequence, based on the encoder's hidden representations. Unlike RNNs that process inputs sequentially, transformers can parallelly process input sequences, making it one of their key advantages. Many computer machine learning systems, including those that comprehend human speech, do picture analysis, and employ voice recognition, frequently use a component of the apparatus called the spectrograph.

H. Spectrogram

Machine learning methods can be used to analyse spectral data and extract relevant features from the data. These algorithms can find patterns in spectral data that are challenging to notice with the naked eye. By examining the patterns and correlations in the spectrum data, machine learning algorithms are able to find individual spectroscopic fingerprints that are unique to particular materials or compounds. Spectrum data analysis and insight extraction are now made possible by machine learning, which was previously impractical or impossible to do. As spectroscopic research develops, machine learning is anticipated to play a bigger role in the analysis and interpretation of spectrum data.

I. Dataset

Here we are Using CSV Files for our model. The fields meanfreq, sd, median, Q25, Q75, IQR, skew, Kurt, sp. ent, sfm, mode, centroid, meanfun, minfun, maxfun, meandom, mind, maxdom, range, modding, label correspond to the sample's gender. Acoustic qualities are specified in the remaining fields. Along with the pre-processed dataset, the training data also includes the raw voice samples. WAV files kept in a different location.

Fig 6 Architecture Diagram

J. Pearson Correlation of Features

Fig 7 Pearson Correlation of Features

The Pearson correlation measures the degree to which two variables have a linear relationship. A value of -1 indicates a total negative linear correlation, a number of 0 means there is no association, while a value of +1 means there is a completely positive correlation.

IV. RESULT

After giving the model a defined input under accurate bounds, the output is generated in terms of Male, Female and Transgender. The precise output is displayed to the user through GUI:

Fig 8 Result

Fig 9 GUI Representing Result

V. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

VOICE GENDER RECOGNITION is the tool we are building to identify the gender of a person based on vocal data and information. In this paper we are presenting the design, the proposed system in this paper and the implementation. Speech and sound specialists have found it challenging to deduce a person's gender based on their voice, even when employing a number of technologies, such as CRM systems' Effective advertising and marketing strategies. Investigating the voice of the culprit in crime scenes. improving conversation systems and other human-computer interaction (HCI) technologies. In the medical sector, diagnosing people with voice issues may be highly helpful. By taking over duties that don't require humans, it increases efficiency. The purpose of acoustic characteristics is to react to sound waves. Gender recognition is a method for figuring out a speaker's gender category. The length, strength, frequency, and filtering of an acoustic signal may be learnt from the signals of a recorded voice. Adaptation of music for waiting rooms so that different kinds of music can be played depending on age and gender. It can help in various other fields like Robotics, finance and banking, computer vision, etc.

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